

DETERMINANTS OF SATISFACTION LEVEL OF KOREAN EMPLOYERS FROM FOREIGN GRADUATES

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Abstract. *Today there are a lot of factors that can impact on having successful career in Korea for foreign graduates, however not all of them can have statistical significance. Conducted research aims to determine the significant variables of satisfaction level of Korean employers from foreign graduates. Surveys, interviews as well as questionnaires have been conducted among Korean employers on satisfaction level, in order to develop conclusion and create guides for stakeholders. The results show that age and Korean language speaking skills, internship period have statistical significance in the first three models, however age and Korean language skills have positive relationship with employer satisfaction which means over years they may learn more about culture and head of the company and increase employers' satisfaction. The factors can be strengthened, that contribute to employee satisfaction and mitigate the factors that contribute to employee dissatisfaction, whether it's the work environment or salary, the relationship between colleagues or the relationship with the supervisor, and how empowering employees and delegating necessary authority enables them to complete the job perfectly*

Key words: *job satisfaction, foreign graduates, employee performance, company employers, strengthen the relationship.*

ДЕТЕРМИНАНТЫ УРОВНЯ УДОВЛЕТВОРЕННОСТИ КОРЕЙСКИХ РАБОТОДАТЕЛЕЙ ИНОСТРАННЫМИ ВЫПУСКНИКАМИ

Аннотация. *Сегодня есть много факторов, которые могут повлиять на успешную карьеру в Корее для иностранных выпускников, однако не все из них могут иметь статистическую значимость. Проведенное исследование направлено на определение значимых переменных уровня удовлетворенности корейских работодателей иностранными выпускниками. Опросы, интервью, а также анкетирование были проведены среди корейских работодателей по уровню удовлетворенности с целью подготовки выводов и создания руководств для заинтересованных сторон. Результаты показывают, что возраст и знание корейского языка, период стажировки имеют статистическую значимость в первых трех моделях, однако возраст и знание корейского языка имеют положительную связь с удовлетворенностью работодателя, что означает, что с годами они могут больше узнать о культуре и руководителе компании и повысить удовлетворенность работодателей. Можно усилить факторы, способствующие удовлетворенности сотрудников, и смягчить факторы, способствующие неудовлетворенности сотрудников, будь то рабочая среда или заработная плата, отношения между коллегами или отношения с руководителем, а также то, как*

расширение возможностей сотрудников и делегирование необходимых полномочий позволяет им чтобы выполнить работу идеально.

Ключевые слова: удовлетворенность работой, иностранные выпускники, эффективность работы сотрудников, компании-работодатели, укрепление отношений.

I. Introduction

Foreign workforce policy in Korea. From the late 1980s onwards, as industrialization and income levels increased, a shortage of low-skilled workers developed. Since the early 1990s, an influx of foreign workers has occurred, primarily as a result of the industrial trainee system. However, poor system management resulted in issues such as corrupt brokers and workers fleeing their jobs. Later, as a result of improvements such as the 2003 introduction of a foreign employment permit system, regulations governing the employment of foreign workers were loosened and employment protections for foreign workers were strengthened. As a result, the number of these workers rapidly increased.

Foreigners with long-term visas who are eligible to work in Korea can be classified into two broad categories under the current employment permit system: non-professionals and professionals. Non-professional workers are typically granted visas for non-professional employment (E-9), working visit (H-2), or compatriot (F-4). After arriving in Korea, foreign workers with working visit and compatriot visas can search for jobs independently, and they can work in a broader range of industries than those with non-professional employment visas. Professional workers are few in number, and language instructors make up the lion's share of them. Foreign worker quotas are currently in place to ensure their orderly entry and management. In the case of the general employment permit system (E-9), each year, industry is assigned a quota of approximately 50,000 new general foreign workers. In the case of foreign workers with working visit (H-2) visas, the total number was 303,000, with a cap on the total.

However, due to the relatively strict requirements for obtaining these visas, approximately 270,000 compatriots were reported to have such visas as of the end of 2016. Manufacturing (45%) employs the largest share of the total foreign workforce, followed by wholesale and retail, restaurants and hotels (20%), business, personal, and public services and others (19%), and construction (19%).¹² (9 percent). Male foreign workers are concentrated in manufacturing (55%), while female foreign workers are concentrated in wholesale and retail, as well as restaurants and hotels (40 percent). When foreign workers are considered as a percentage of total employment, they make up a much larger proportion of the manufacturing sector, as well as the business, personal, and public services sectors, which include workers dispatched by temporary work agencies.

Graduate employment studies defined generic competencies as the skills, abilities, and characteristics that employees need to perform their jobs effectively. Employers prefer candidates who possess generic competencies such as interpersonal and leadership abilities (Mason, 1992). Raymond (1993) conducted a survey of students and employers to ascertain their perceptions of the most critical entry-level employee skills. Employers ranked oral skills, dependability, interpersonal skills, written skills, and self-starter/motivation as the top five essential skills and abilities for success (in order of relative importance). Interestingly, students ranked oral communication skills, interpersonal communication skills, dependability, motivation, and written

communication skills as the most important. Levenburg (1996) interviewed business school faculty and practitioners to ascertain the general management skills that business school graduates should possess. Oral and written communication abilities, presentation abilities, multimedia presentation abilities, teamwork, initiative, honesty and integrity, dependability, technical report writing, research/library skills, global awareness, decision-making abilities, computer skills, leadership, problem analysis and project management abilities, and multicultural appreciation were all evaluated.

Thornburg (1997) identified the following success skills: oral communication, written communication, computer literacy, problem solving, interpersonal relations, leadership, and delegation. Tanyel (1999) noted that the most important characteristics that newly recruited business school graduates should possess (in order of importance) are responsibility and accountability, ethical values, interpersonal skills, oral communication, time management and punctuality, and the ability to work in teams. Similarly, among university faculty respondents, the most important attributes are responsibility and accountability, oral communication, interpersonal skills, written communication, creativity and critical thinking, time management and punctuality, and decision-making and analytical ability.

According to the literature review on the satisfaction level, (Yoon, et al., 2020) use the variables dividing them into three groups: personal information (gender, age, higher education type, GPA, school location), satisfaction with the quality of higher education, participation in career development goals (job training program, internship, etc). However this research is about the satisfaction level of graduates from the job. It can be used in the current research as well. Those graduates who have internship are more satisfied than those who just having short term programs. Jisun & Lee (2016) determined that university prestige also impacts on satisfaction level.

Foreign workers are frequently preferred over Korean workers if their job skills or work capacities are comparable, owing to the lower reservation wages paid to foreign workers. This is why, with the exception of highly skilled foreign workers with professional expertise, the majority of countries protect their citizens' labor markets by emphasizing the role of foreign workforce inflow as a complement to the domestic labor market. In other words, countries seek to mitigate the negative consequences of foreign workers entering their labor markets by placing them primarily in sectors avoided by domestic workers (Lee & Park, 2008).

1.1 Purpose of the study:

To conduct literature review on determinants of Korean employers' satisfaction from foreign graduates;

To determine whether Korean companies need foreign graduates and what requirements employers have;

To analyze the determinants of satisfaction level of Korean employers from foreign graduates;

To develop conclusions and recommendation according to the research results

1.2. Research questions

What are the factors that impact on the satisfaction level of Korean employers from foreign graduates?

How can foreign graduates increase the satisfaction level of Korean employers from their performance?

II. Review of Literature

Preferred Attributes by Employers. Employing new employees is a critical task for any business. As a result, employers prefer applicants who can work independently quickly in the absence of an in-house training program (Kelley & Gaedeke, 1990; Webster & Taylor, 1995). This is understandable, as accepted applicants are expected to take on the job with little supervision. This is not always the case, however. For instance, a study conducted in four European countries discovered that employers were skeptical of graduates' abilities in key knowledge areas and generic competencies (Azevedo, et al., 2012). Numerous countries have developed a comprehensive account of how skills are used and how organizational practices contribute to the development of these skills or help eliminate skill imbalances and low-skills traps (OECD, 2012a). Indeed, the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) places a premium on the three pillars of skills strategy, namely developing relevant skills, activating the skills supply, and putting skills to effective use (OECD, 2012a), in order to ensure that graduates are employable and prepared for work. Employers desire employees who possess the necessary skills or characteristics for the job for which they have been hired. Though companies have varying job requirements, the debate over employability and what employers want continues (Bills, Di Stasio, & Grxhani, 2017; Cumming, 2010; Cunningham & Villaseor, 2016; Frankham, 2017; McQuiad & Lindasy, 2005; Tymon, 2013).

Employability, as defined by the Confederation of British Industry (1999, as cited in Bridgstock, 2009), is "the individual's possession of the qualities and competencies necessary to meet the changing needs of employers and customers" (p. 32-33). Numerous attempts have been made to provide a more comprehensive understanding of it. For example, Finch, Hamilton, Baldwin, and Zehner (2013) discovered two levels of understanding employability when conducting a review of the literature. These included both specific employability skills (e.g., listening abilities, writing abilities, and academic performance) and higher-level categories. They identified five factors under higher-order categories: soft skills; problem-solving abilities; job-specific functional abilities; pre-graduate experience; and academic reputation. In a similar vein, Osmani et al. (2015) reviewed 39 articles on employability published in Scopus journals and discovered 53 graduate characteristics. The most significant ones were communication, teamwork, problem-solving, technological abilities, creativity, interpersonal abilities, leadership abilities, self-management, and adaptability/flexibility.

Performance. Performance is a fundamental and critical concept for organizations in general, serving as the common denominator for management scientists' attention; it is almost a phenomenon inclusiveness and a central element of all distinctions and fields of administrative knowledge, as well as the most significant dimension of various organizations, revolving around the organization's existence or non-existence (Al- Chaoui, 2010). Organizational growth has increased and broadened the scope of work, occupying the theme of performance as an area of interest for thinkers and practitioners, and becoming the subject of a number of academic studies. It is a core activity of human resource management, including human resource planning, selection, appointment, determining salaries and wages, and other activities (Abu-Nasr, 2008). Farooqui and Nagendra (2014) noted that an organization's performance is highly dependent on the job performance of its employees. When an employee is inefficient, he or she has poor functional performance, and as a result, the tact with which they speak and communicate information can be

an indicator of his or her performance at work, as this skill will reflect positively on their work results and strengthen the relationship with their direct manager. Employee performance evaluation is a critical topic in the managerial process because it motivates administrative systems to work energetically and actively, where it requires managers to monitor their subordinates' duties and responsibilities on a continuous basis, and motivates subordinates to work effectively. It also demonstrates the importance of this medium when examining the areas that make use of the performance evaluation results, and most importantly, it demonstrates the importance of this medium when examining the areas that make use of the performance evaluation results (Abu Sheikha, 2010).

Concept of job performance. Job performance refers to the degree to which an individual achieves and completes tasks that are part of his or her function, and reflects how the tasks can be accomplished or how the individual can meet his or her job requirements. Often, the distinction between performance and effort is unambiguous, with effort referring to the energy expended and performance based on the results achieved by an individual. For example, a student may expend considerable effort to prepare for a test (Abu crack 0.2010).

Andreia (2012) noted that job performance is the most critical functional outcome, and he defines job performance as the accumulated value from activities in which the employee will participate directly and individually in achieving organizational goals, either positively or negatively. According to Al-Taamnh (2009), job performance is the most critical professional work axis in any functional area; if this performance is exceptional in light of the work environment's commitment to justice and equality, it makes sense to elevate this performance to a prominent position within the organization in which he works; and in a world of rapid change and intense competition, organizations cannot compete unless high performance is one of their most important characteristics. Al-Sarairh et al. (2009) defined performance as the result of two interaction factors, namely ability and motivation. In the absence of motivation, an individual's ability to perform work improperly, and if he has the motivation to work without ability, he cannot perform as he should. Al-Dawy (2009) defined performance as an act that results in the work being performed properly; this act is characterized by unmatched and continuous effort, or by acting in a manner that results in the achievement of predetermined goals. Grandey (2013) demonstrates that workplace rewards are more powerful when accompanied by pay-for-performance incentives and commissions. As such, bonuses may reinforce good performance behaviors while decreasing intrinsic motivation to perform. Intrinsic motivation to perform is derived from the satisfaction and joy associated with engaging in the same activity.

Job Satisfaction. The success of organizations is largely determined by the effectiveness with which individual employees perform their functions and duties, which is influenced by their level of job satisfaction, because it is entirely natural for individual performance to vary when an employee is satisfied with his or her work, when an employee is dissatisfied with his or her work, or when an employee believes that his or her employer is unconcerned about his or her level of satisfaction.

The subject of job satisfaction piqued the interest of researchers in the fields of management, psychology, and other sciences, resulting in the emergence of a plethora of research and studies examining the concept of job satisfaction of the individual and determining the factors

that contribute to satisfaction, and then achieving both his own and his work's objectives in a complementary and interactive manner (Adel, 2010).

The physical work environment is critical for performance and employee satisfaction. When the work environment is unfavorable, it can result in feelings of stress and pressure, which can affect their performance at work. As a result, heterogeneous physical changes in employees have an effect on their performance at work. As a result, changes to certain aspects of the work environment, such as lighting, may result in an increase or decrease in employee performance. Additionally, it was noted that exposure to noise, for example, has a detrimental effect on one's sense of hearing, which can impair an employee's performance (Vischer, 2007).

Erkutlu (2008) discovered that employees perform better and feel better when responding to workload when they believe they receive adequate compensation for their efforts. Additionally, some believed that unfair and biased treatment constitutes significant pressure on the employee, has a negative psychological and social impact on the employee, and thus contributes to prejudiced behaviors and attitudes toward work.

Job satisfaction can be determined by an employee's behavior in the institutions where they work, and this behavior is closely related to employee relations with employers and coworkers, where job satisfaction is critical in industrial enterprises, as evidenced by the need to improve employee work satisfaction (Soleimani et al., 2011).

Job satisfaction is one of the terms used to describe whether employees were satisfied and convinced investigators of their desires and needs, as some measures indicate that job satisfaction is a factor of motivation and a factor in achieving one's objectives, and is also considered an important factor in developing an employee's positive work ethics (Bin Hussin, 2011).

The concept of Job Satisfaction. The modern behavioral school contributed to the development of the job satisfaction concept by viewing it as a response to multiple factors, including job satisfaction, as well as the content and circumstances of those factors. They believe that in order to understand job satisfaction, it is necessary to study job dimensions and standards, which include employment, salary, promotion, and working conditions, supervision, and coworkers. Numerous definitions have been published in an attempt to clarify the meaning of job satisfaction, but there is no standard definition due to the multiplicity of studies and research that have addressed this subject in unique ways; each of them attempts to develop a concept that is consistent with the requirements of his or her research or study; additionally, the issue of job satisfaction is frequently viewed as a personal and relative one, due to the fact that Thus, the most critical definitions will be contained in order to address this concept.

Job satisfaction has multiple dimensions and is influenced by a variety of factors, some of which are related to the work itself, while others are related to group work and the surrounding work environment. It is a mistake to believe that just because an individual is satisfied with one aspect of his work, he is necessarily satisfied with the rest of the job and its dimensions. Job satisfaction is a relative rather than absolute concept, as there is no upper or lower limit, and the sensation of satisfaction is the result of the interaction between the individual's desires and what actually occurs in a particular position (Shawish, 2011).

Numerous studies have been conducted to determine employee satisfaction, as employee satisfaction results in effective participation in the quality and excellence of organizational performance, and there is a strong correlation between employee satisfaction and the effectiveness

of their performance. (Piriyanthanalai&Muenjohn, 2012) and Wahyudi et al. (2013) noted that job satisfaction can be defined as a generalization of an employee's attitude toward the work performed, which encompasses a variety of factors, and thus the employee's attitude toward his work reflects both positive and negative work experiences, as well as future expectations.

According to Piriyanthanalai and Muenjohn (2012, p90), job satisfaction is an employee's overall assessment of his or her work, which is influenced by the employee's work location, incentives and control mechanisms, and management system. Wang (2012) defines job satisfaction as an employee's actions, responses, personal feelings, and physical and intellectual position in relation to the work environment, as well as the general attitude toward his or her job duties.

Mansouri (2010) defines job satisfaction as 'the sum of what an employee expects from his work and what happens to him, the result of which explains his job satisfaction'. While Abdul Ghani (2008) defines job satisfaction as an employee's acceptance of his or her work in all circumstances and conditions, this acceptance reflects the employee's feelings about the work they are performing, and satisfaction results in increased production and achievement along with normal tension (positive). Dissatisfaction results in unequal tension (negative) and a lack of motivation for production.

According to Liham (2009), job satisfaction is determined by the employees' negative and positive attitudes toward their work or certain aspects of their work. Employee job satisfaction reflects an individual's emotional reaction to a particular job, and if an organization wishes to increase production and improve performance, it should place a premium on employee job satisfaction, as ignoring satisfaction factors would imply ignoring a sizable portion of the organization's objectives. (2012) (Piriyanthanalai&Muenjohn).

Kermani (2013) defines job satisfaction as a pleasurable and positive emotional state that results from an employee's evaluation of his or her work and practical experience. Here, we can strengthen the factors that contribute to employee satisfaction and mitigate the factors that contribute to employee dissatisfaction, whether it's the work environment or salary, the relationship between colleagues or the relationship with the supervisor, and how empowering employees and delegating necessary authority enables them to complete the job perfectly.

III. Method

Type of research. The research studies the factors affecting employer satisfactions from foreign graduates in Korea. As mentioned above Korean companies are attractive to foreigners in terms of working conditions and salary opportunities. In the research the relationship between dependent and independent variables will be checked. The variables will be chosen according to the literature review. Satisfaction level of employers is a dependent variable and it is measured in a Likert scale 1 to 5. The characteristic of variables is shown in the following table. In order to collect data, the survey is conducted and analyzed in STATA.

Variables		Measurement
Control variables	Age	criterion variable
	Years of schooling	After high school years

	Control of origin	English speaking country =1 Non-English-speaking country=0
Independent variables	Language skills: Listening skills (Korean)	criterion variable
	Writing skills (Korean)	
	Speaking skills (Korea)	
	University prestige: SKY Universities graduates or not	SKY Universities graduate = 1, Others=0
	Internship	How long he/she had an internship in Korea
	Wage	The average monthly salary (Ln form)
	Punctuality	Whether employers are satisfied from graduates in terms of meeting deadlines (5 point Likert scale)
Dependent variable	Overall satisfaction from a worker	Five-point Likert scale

Table 1. Variable sources

In the research different questions are used, especially those that are considered to be control variables, such as gender, age, country of origin. As dependent variables language skills in terms of listening, writing and speaking are used, and they are measured by the five-point Likert scale to differentiate. In order to check the University Prestige is used, because employers tend to pay more salaries for the graduates of prestigious universities. Having an internship in Korea is also important factor, because graduates get to know Korean culture and traditions, ethics. It will help them to get used to new company faster. Wage is used as an average amount for a month to estimate if employers are satisfied from the performance of the workers for the salaries they pay. As dependent variable overall satisfaction level of the employer is measured using five-point Likert scale.

Data source:

Overall satisfaction of employers from the performance of employees

Data on this variable is collected through survey and it measures in general how Korean employers are satisfied from the work performance of foreign graduates.

Language skills. Korean language skills are important even though English is widely spoken in South Korea, still speaking Korean is appreciated and gives comparative advantage. The data on this variable is divided on three sub categories such as speaking skills, listening skills, writing skills of Korean language and measurement of it also used five-point Likert scale.

Internship period. Internship while studying is not obligatory in Korea, however foreigners may learn more about Korean companies' corporate culture, employee expectations and working ethics during internship period, therefore the period of internship is also checked it is measured by the days of internship period.

University prestige. The SKY abbreviation is the first letters of the names of South Korea's most respected universities: Seoul National University, Korea University, and Yonsei University. It is believed that absolutely all graduates of these universities get a high-paying job, and at the same time a privileged status in society. There are several reasons why SKY universities are so popular such as ranking, tuition fee, international environment. I would like to check if the university prestige has a statistical significance on the satisfaction level of Korean employees. It is considered as a dummy variable.

Wage. Although there are certain standards in Korea regarding salaries, in some cases it is negotiated between employers and employees. Therefore, we would like to check if this variable is statistically significant and the sign of the relationship. It is measured ln of monthly average salary of the employees

Punctuality. One of the most appreciated qualities by employers is punctuality. It means how foreign employees meet deadline set by employers.

Econometric model. Perhaps the most frequently used statistical technique in the social sciences is regression analysis. Regression is a technique for determining the relationship between two or more object attributes. By defining and quantifying attitudes, you can gain a better understanding of what is happening on the ground, forecast where something will occur, and begin testing the reasons why events occur in the places they do.

OLS is the most widely used method for regression analysis. Additionally, it serves as a good starting point for all spatial regression techniques. The method entails the construction of a global model of the variable or process being studied or predicted; he then generates a regression equation that reflects the process as it occurs.

Regression model

$$ES = \beta_0 + \ln\beta_1 WAGE + \beta_2 AGE + \beta_3 YOS + \beta_4 UNIP + \beta_5 KLS + \beta_6 KLL + \beta_7 KLW + \beta_8 PUNC + \beta_9 INT + \beta_{10} COO + u_t$$

This regression model checks the relationship between dependent and independent variables. ES-employer satisfaction level, WAGE – ln of wages of employees monthly, AGE – average age of foreign graduates who work for the company, YOS – years of schooling after high school, KLS – Korean language skills speaking, KLL – Korean language skills – listening, KLW – Korean language skills writing, PUNC – how employers are satisfied from the ability of meeting deadlines, INT – number of days of internship while studying in Korea before beginning to work, COO – country of origin is English spoken country or not.

I. Results and discussion

This chapter includes the analysis of the results of the regression and summary statistics of the data. For the analysis more than 60 companies have been questioned out of them 34 participated

in the survey. Data have been adjusted to STATA software to run regression analysis. Overall, 11 questions have been developed and used in the survey.

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
ES	34	3.529412	1.186676	1	5
AGE	34	35.32353	9.087856	22	51
YOS	34	5.320588	1.094	4	8
COO	34	0.558824	0.503995	0	1
KLS	34	3.617647	0.95393	2	5
KLW	34	2.882353	0.879556	1	5
KLL	34	3.235294	1.182161	1	5
UNIP	34	0.411765	0.499554	0	1
INT	34	46.20588	26.58409	0	90
PUNC	34	4.470588	0.748141	3	5
WAGE	34	3350882	564926.2	2500000	5000000

Table 2. Descriptive statistics without logarithm the wage
Source: Author's calculations

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INT	34	46.20588	26.58409	0	90
PUNC	34	4.470588	0.748141	3	5
logWage	34	15.01168	0.162165	14.7318	15.42495

Table 3. Descriptive statistics with logarithm the wage
Source: Author's calculations

Table 3 shows the number of observations, means and standard deviations, minimum and maximum values of the variables. But one difference with table 2 is I used the log value for wage.

Figure 1. Graph matrix of variables
Source: Author's calculations

	ES	AGE	YOS	COO	KLS	KLV	KLL	UNIP	INT	PUNC	<u>logWage</u>
ES	1										
AGE	0.7929	1									
YOS	0.4839	0.4221	1								
COO	0.0984	0.2174	0.3028	1							
KLS	0.3181	0.1475	0.5072	0.2688	1						
KLV	0.2066	0.1262	0.3175	0.0161	0.7032	1					
KLL	0.3837	0.2719	0.364	0.1286	0.7271	0.6686	1				
UNIP	0.0812	0.2034	0.0117	0.1416	0.1496	0.1136	0.0362	1			
INT	-0.0852	0.2152	0.0691	0.2218	0.0653	0.0166	0.0813	0.1121	1		
PUNC	0.5301	0.5251	0.5617	0.1655	0.3022	0.2709	0.2822	-0.1288	0.2662	1	
<u>logWage</u>	0.4899	0.5891	0.5697	0.382	0.1405	0.1395	0.2833	0.1034	0.2896	0.38	1

Figure 2. Correlation matrix

According to the correlation matrix, we can say that there is no problem of multicollinearity. Multicollinearity occurs when independent variables in a regression model are correlated. This correlation is a problem because independent variables should be independent. If the degree of correlation between variables is high enough, it can cause problems when you fit the model and interpret the results. From the correlation matrix there is slightly higher positive correlation with employer satisfaction and age of the foreign graduates.

Variable	VIF	1/VIF
KLS	4.21	0.237703
KLL	2.87	0.34858
YOS	2.76	0.362271
logWage	2.58	0.386934
KLW	2.45	0.408974
PUNC	2.12	0.472239
AGE	2.09	0.477645
COO	1.41	0.709307
UNIP	1.28	0.782522
INT	1.25	0.797372
Mean VIF	2.3	

Figure 3. VIF test results

Variance inflation coefficients range from one to ten. The numerical value for VIF indicates the percentage by which the variance (i.e. the standard error squared) is inflated for each coefficient (in decimal form). For instance, a VIF of 1.9 indicates that the variance of a particular coefficient is 90% larger than what would be expected in the absence of multicollinearity — in the absence of correlation with other predictors. The exact size of a VIF that must exist before causing problems is debatable. What is known is that as your VIF increases, your regression results become less reliable. In general, a VIF greater than 10 indicates a high degree of correlation and should raise concern. Certain authors advocate for a more conservative level of 2.5 or greater.

Occasionally, a high VIF is of no concern. For instance, you can obtain a high VIF by including products or powers of other variables, such as x and x^2 , in your regression. If you have a high VIF for dummy variables that represent nominal variables with three or more categories, this is typically not a problem.

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
VARIABLES	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3	Model 4	Model 5	Model 6
AGE	0.0933***	0.0922***	0.0898***	0.0905***		

	(0.0171)	(0.0201)	(0.0170)	(0.0185)		
YOS	-0.0410	0.0876	0.0604		0.0365	0.0365
	(0.166)	(0.159)	(0.162)		(0.191)	(0.191)
COO	-0.257	-0.160	-0.168	-0.147	-0.221	-0.221
	(0.229)	(0.271)	(0.238)	(0.242)	(0.400)	(0.400)
KLS	0.277*					
	(0.140)					
UNIP	-0.101	-0.0309	-0.0176		0.359	0.359
	(0.227)	(0.226)	(0.229)		(0.269)	(0.269)
INT	- 0.0134***	- 0.0130***	-0.0131***	- 0.0139***	- 0.0147**	-0.0147**
	(0.00398)	(0.00442)	(0.00418)	(0.00428)	(0.00707)	(0.00707)
PUNC	0.238	0.256	0.256	0.343*	0.762***	0.762***
	(0.207)	(0.243)	(0.226)	(0.195)	(0.248)	(0.248)
logWage	0.991	0.526	0.463	0.829	2.954***	2.954***
	(0.678)	(0.725)	(0.697)	(0.782)	(0.856)	(0.856)
KLW		0.0615				
		(0.139)				
KLL			0.147			
			(0.112)			
Constant	-15.69	-8.703	-7.833	-12.92	- 43.75***	-43.75***
	(9.731)	(10.44)	(10.03)	(11.35)	(12.50)	(12.50)
Observations	34	34	34	34	34	34
R-squared	0.777	0.746	0.762	0.740	0.500	0.500

Robust standard errors in parentheses				
*** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1				

Figure 4. Regression results.

IV. CONCLUSION

In order to check the relationship between variables, OLS method has been used and results have been obtained. In the regression results, I have developed 6 models to determine statistically significant variables for the employer satisfaction level. According to the results of correlation matrix and VIF test, we ran different regression models. In the first three models' language skills questions have been used separately. In the last three models some variables have been excluded to check.

The results show that age and Korean language speaking skills, internship period have statistical significance in the first three models, however age and Korean language skills have positive relationship with employer satisfaction which means over years they may learn more about culture and head of the company and increase employers' satisfaction. Internship period has a negative relationship with employer satisfaction. It can be explained that expectation of employers from those who had an internship is high, however if employees do not meet their expectations, employers may get unsatisfied from employees.

Except speaking other language skill elements such as writing and listening are not statistically significant to dependent variable. When I excluded the age variable which is highly correlated with dependent variable, another variable also became significant. They are wage and punctuality. They both have positive relationship with dependent variable. Korean employers that pay high salaries to foreign graduates are satisfied from their employees. Punctuality is also appreciated by Korean employers. But the country of origin, university prestige years of schooling do not have statistical significance with dependent variables.

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